

Sentiment Analysis of Public Feedback Using Natural Language Processing

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Abstract—The goal of this project is to provide a comprehensive and efficient system for expert rating. This program implements a sentiment analysis-based expert rating system. The `SentimentIntensityAnalyzer` and the `nlTK` library are used to compute the sentiment score of expert reviews. The review text has been stripped of stop words and numerals to concentrate only on the text itself. Based on the sentiment scores of the reviews, an overall rating for the expert is produced. The initiative has a mechanism in place for paying specialists who have a particular amount of favorable reviews and a high rating.

Keywords- Expert Rating, Natural Language Processing, `SentimentIntensityAnalyzer`, `nlTK`, Feedback

I. INTRODUCTION

This research focuses on sentiment analysis, which is the automatic detection and classification of the feelings conveyed in the text. Due to its wide applications in a variety of industries, including social media monitoring, customer feedback research, and product reviews, sentiment analysis has attracted a lot of interest recently.

The goal of this project is to create a sentiment analysis model utilizing machine learning algorithms and natural language processing (NLP) methods. For text preprocessing, including tokenization, stop word removal, and stemming, the model makes use of the NLTK library. In order to determine each review's polarity score, the processed data is then passed into a machine learning algorithm, specifically the `SentimentIntensityAnalyzer` from the NLTK toolkit.

Overall, this project intends to provide a trustworthy and effective platform for user feedback analysis while also contributing to continuing work to enhance sentiment analysis methodologies.

II. NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

Artificial intelligence (AI) has a subject called natural language processing (NLP) that focuses on how computers and human language interact. It entails the creation of algorithms and methodologies for the analysis and comprehension of human language in its different

manifestations, such as speech and writing.

A strong Python package that offers a variety of tools for natural language processing (NLP) is called the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK). The ability of NLTK to eliminate stop words from text data, a crucial step in data processing for NLP jobs, is one of its major functions.

NLP Tasks

Speech Recognition: The process of accurately translating voice data into text is known as speech recognition, commonly referred to as speech-to-text. Any programme that responds to voice commands or questions must use speech recognition. The way individuals speak—quickly, slurring words together, with varied emphasis and intonation, in various dialects, and frequently using improper grammar—makes speech recognition particularly difficult.

Part Of Speech Tagging: The act of identifying a word's part of speech based on its use and context is known as part of speech tagging, also known as grammatical tagging. In the sentences "I can make a paper plane" and "What make of car do you own?," the word "make" is classified as a verb and a noun, respectively.

Word Sense Disambiguation: Word sense disambiguation is the act of choosing a word's meaning from among its possible meanings using semantic analysis to discover which word makes the most sense in the context at hand. Disambiguation of word senses, for instance, aids in separating the meanings of the verbs "make" in "make the grade" (achieve) and "make a bet" (place)

The sentiment analysis algorithm being used is the VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and Sentiment Reasoner) algorithm, which is a rule-based approach for sentiment analysis in natural language processing. The VADER algorithm uses a lexicon of words and phrases that have been labeled with positive, negative, and neutral sentiment scores, which were determined by a group of human annotators. The lexicon contains more than 7,500 words and phrases, with each word or phrase being assigned a polarity score between -1 and +1, where -1 represents the most negative sentiment and +1 represents the most positive sentiment. Overall, the VADER algorithm is widely used for sentiment analysis in various applications, particularly in social media analysis. It has been shown to be effective in identifying the sentiment of short, informal texts with high accuracy, and is considered one of the most popular and reliable sentiment analysis tools available.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sentiment analysis has become increasingly relevant in today's world with the rise of social media and online communication, as it allows businesses and individuals to gauge public opinion and make data-driven decisions. Many researchers are going on to find out better alternatives due to its importance.

In a study by, Garg, N., Gupta, P., & Mittal, N. [1] (2020) , sentiment analysis methods for social media opinion mining are reviewed, with an emphasis on approaches that make use of NLP and machine learning algorithms. The authors talk about using VADER to analyse sentiment in social media data and contrast its effectiveness with that of other sentiment analysis programmes. They also note the difficulties and potential directions in this field.

In a study by Pandey, S., & Yadav, S. [2] (2022), With a focus on NLP techniques and machine learning algorithms, the authors assessed various sentiment analysis methods for product reviews. They outlined the advantages and disadvantages of several approaches, including the usage of VADER for sentiment analysis, while discussing the research gaps and potential future directions.

In a study by Chen, X., & Zhou, X [3] (2021 Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA), which entails recognising the elements of a good or service that are mentioned in a review and figuring out the sentiment connected with each one, was thoroughly reviewed. The authors explored applications in diverse disciplines, aspect extraction methods, sentiment categorization methods, and opinion summarising methods in their discussion of contemporary ABSA work.

A study by Qadir, T. A., & Raza, M. [4] (2021), With an emphasis on NLP techniques and machine learning algorithms, the authors examined various sentiment analysis strategies for product reviews with a focus on sentiment polarity categorization.

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A study by Alam, M. R., & Chowdhury, M. M. R. [5] (2021), In this work, sentiment analysis methods for social media opinion mining are reviewed, with an emphasis on approaches that make use of NLP and machine learning algorithms. The authors talk about using VADER to analyse sentiment in social media data and contrast its effectiveness with that of other sentiment analysis programmes. They also note the difficulties and potential directions in this field.

IV. MOTIVATION

It enables you to examine the sentiments and opinions expressed in client testimonials regarding the expert's performance, sentiment analysis can be a helpful technique for determining the expert rating on a question-answer website. You may determine the expert's strengths and weaknesses and learn more about the variables that affect client perceptions and ratings by analysing the sentiment of customer reviews.

You can get a more precise and reliable measurement of the general sentiment towards the expert's performance by using sentiment analysis to determine the expert rating. This can be especially helpful for question-and-answer websites, where the calibre of the expert responses is a key element in luring and keeping customers. Additionally, automating the expert rating process with the aid of sentiment analysis and NLP can help you save time and resources. Sentiment analysis enables you to analyse a big number of evaluations in a systematic and automated way rather than depending on manual ratings or surveys, which can provide you a more complete and accurate picture of the customers' sentiments and opinions.

Overall, sentiment analysis utilising NLP can be a useful tool for determining the expert rating on a question-answer website because it enables systematic, automated analysis of a sizable volume of textual data and offers insights into the variables affecting users' perceptions and ratings of the expert's performance.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Given a database of experts and their associated reviews, the code performs sentiment analysis on the reviews using the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) library. The sentiment analysis involves calculating a sentiment score for each review categorizing the sentiment score as positive, negative, or neutral based on a threshold, and aggregating the sentiment scores for all the reviews associated with each expert to calculate an average sentiment score. The average sentiment score is then used to update the expert's rating field in the database. The code also removes digits from the text data before performing sentiment analysis to ensure that numbers

Average sentimental score with negative review

Category : SCIENCE
Question: father of science?
Expected Date : Nov. 30, 2022
Expert Name : anjaly
Rating : 39

[View Proof of expert](#)

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Fig 2

In this section, [Fig 2] The method uses the SentimentIntensityAnalyzer class from the NLTK library to apply a sentiment analysis model after preprocessing each review's text by removing stopwords and digits. Here a negative review was added . So after taking the sentimental score the average was below 50.

Average sentimental score with positive review

Category : SCIENCE
Question: father of science?
Expected Date : Nov. 30, 2022
Expert Name : anjaly
Rating : 55

[View Proof of expert](#)

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In this section, [Fig 3] The method uses the SentimentIntensityAnalyzer class from the NLTK library to apply a sentiment analysis model after preprocessing each review's text by removing stopwords and digits. Here a positive review was added . So after taking the sentimental score the average was above 50.

VII. CONCLUSION

The code's sentiment analysis method can be used to determine an expert's rating on a question-and-answer website based on user feedback. The Vader sentiment analyzer and the Natural Language Processing (NLP) method are used to perform the sentiment analysis. The code repeatedly loops over each expert in the database, calculating their grade by examining the tone of the reviews they have amassed.

Additionally, the seminar paper could go over the potential advantages of using sentiment analysis to rate experts on question-answer websites, including the provision of more accurate and objective ratings, enhancement of the user experience, and improvement of customer satisfaction. The paper should also go into the drawbacks and difficulties of sentiment analysis, such as its accuracy, the possibility of bias in the evaluations, and the necessity of routine modifications to the sentiment analysis model.

Overall, the seminar paper might offer a thorough introduction of sentiment analysis' advantages, constraints, and possible applications for assessing experts on question-answer websites

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